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Chitosan treatments for the fishery industry – Enhancing quality and safety of fishery products

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<i>Ágríp á íslensku:</i>	<p>Þessi skýrsla er samantekt þriggja geymslupólstilrauna þar sem sjávarfang var meðhöndlað með mismunandi kítósan-lausnum, annars vegar um borð veiðiskips (með rækju og þorski) eða eftir slátrun og forvinnslu eldislaxs. Þetta er framhald af skýrslu Matís 41-12 þar sem kítósan-lausnir voru þróaðar og prófaðar á mismunandi fiskafurðum á tilraunastigi hjá Matís. Tilgangur þessa verkefnis var að staðfesta notkunarmöguleika kítósan-meðhöndlunar á sjávarfangi í fiskiðnaðinum. Niðurstöður sýna að styrkleikur kítósan-lausna og geymsluhitastig sjávarfangs hafa áhrif á örverudrepandi virkni og gæðarýrnun fiskafurðanna. Lausnir A og B höfðu takmarkaða virkni í heilum rækjum (0-1°C), en hægari litabreytingar áttu sér stað þar sem skelin tók upp svartan lit. Meðhöndlun laxa (1.4°C) og þorska (-0.2°C) með lausnum C og D hægði verulega á vexti roðbaktería fyrstu 6 dagana sem leiddi til lengingar á fersleikafasanum. Geymsluhitastig þorskfiska hafði áhrif á virkni lausnanna. Þegar þorskur (2-3°C) var geymdur við verri aðstæður og flakaður 6 dögum eftir meðhöndlun, reyndist vera aðeins minna örveruálág á flökunum í upphafi geymslutímans sem skilaði sig lítillega í gæðum afurðanna. Betri geymsluskilyrði eru nauðsynleg til að kámarka virkni kítósan-meðferðar.</p>		
<i>Lykilorð á íslensku:</i>	<i>kítósan – bakteríudrepandi – lenging ferskleika – matvælaöryggi – gæði</i>		
<i>Summary in English:</i>	<p>This report evaluates the efficiency of different chitosan treatments (A, B, C, D) when used by fishery companies, aiming to reduce seafood surface contamination and promote enhanced quality of fishery products: whole cod, shrimp and farmed salmon. The alkaline conditions establishing in chilled raw shrimp during storage (0-1°C) is the probable cause for no benefits of chitosan treatments A and B used shortly after catch, except for the slower blackening of head and shell observed compared to the control group. On the other hand, salmon treatments C and D were most effective in significantly reducing skin bacterial load up to 6 days post-treatment (1.4°C) which inevitably contributed to the extended freshness period (by 4 days) and shelf life observed. Similarly, freshness extension and delayed bacterial growth on skin was evidenced after 6 days of storage in whole cod (-0.2°C) treated with solution D. For cod stored at higher temperature (2-3°C) and processed into loins on days 3 and 6 post-treatment, a slower microbial deterioration was observed only during early storage of loins. The contribution of chitosan treatments to sensory quality enhancement was not clearly demonstrated in these products. Based on the findings, better chilling conditions should contribute to an enhanced effect of chitosan skin treatment towards quality maintenance.</p>		
<i>English keywords:</i>	<i>chitosan – antibacterial effect – freshness extension – food safety – quality</i>		

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1. INTRODUCTION

Fresh seafood has a short shelf life due to growth of opportunistic spoilage bacteria that takes place during storage and distribution to retailers. Pathogenic bacteria can further pose public threat especially if storage and handling conditions are inadequate. Fish flesh becomes contaminated following storage of whole fish and/or during processing. The main cause of bacterial contamination of fish processing line is due to rapid bacterial proliferation on the skin during storage which spreads during filleting and by post-contamination during processing. Reducing the microbiota before process and preventing its development during storage will extend shelf life of fishery products. The limited shelf life of fish is a large hurdle for their commerce and distribution worldwide. Fish are much more perishable than meat, due to flesh composition (neutral pH, low carbohydrate concentration, high content in non-protein low molecular weight nitrogenous molecules) favoring the growth of Gram-negative spoilage bacteria.

Temperature control and reduction of bacterial contamination are the key factors because the bacteria found on the surface of newly caught or slaughtered fish will proliferate according to time and temperature. The extension of seafood freshness period is in fact the most valuable achievement, as it will allow a longer time for distribution and sale of high quality products. Observation across many shelf life studies on fresh fish has demonstrated that a tenfold higher initial load of specific spoilage bacteria on fillets will reduce their shelf life by at least one day under refrigerated conditions (Lauzon *et al.* 2010). Therefore, as a basic principle, handling procedures and techniques to minimize bacterial growth on fish once harvested are of great value. Indeed, proliferation of spoilage bacteria on fish skin can increase 100-fold to 1000-fold after 4-5 days of storage on ice (Reynisson *et al.* 2010). Further, poor temperature control will lead to a more rapid growth of spoilage bacteria and loss of fish freshness.

The safety of some fishery products may be compromised as current practice does not inhibit or reduce the growth of food-borne pathogens. *Listeria monocytogenes* is a major pathogen in ready-to-eat seafood products, with 30 to 45% fatality rate. Its prevalence in cold-smoked salmon is high (Chitlapilly Dass *et al.* 2010) due to contamination of the raw material itself and cross-contamination during handling and processing. *L. monocytogenes* can grow over a wide range of temperature, pH and salt and therefore develop during storage of seafood, sometimes overpassing the limit of 100 cells/g tolerated in Europe.

Biopreservation is a natural preservation technology consisting in the use of preservative techniques based on natural means aiming to reduce microbial load and enhance quality and safety. Chitosan, a natural biopolymer, has been suggested as a novel food biopreservative due to its broad antimicrobial spectrum (Roller and Covill 1999), biodegradability and non-toxicity (Coma *et al.* 2002). A recent European project (HURDLETECH within the integrated project SEAFOODplus, No FOOD CT-2004-506359) evaluated some commercial chitosan products and concluded that food grade ChitoClear® chitosan (Primex, Iceland) could inhibit or retard the growth of pathogenic and spoilage bacteria isolated from seafood (Cruz *et al.* 2006). These findings triggered research cooperation (AVS contracts R11 074-11 and R13 099-13) between Primex and Matís, to evaluate different applications for the seafood industry. One application implies coating the

skin of newly caught or slaughtered fish with chitosan to reduce bacterial proliferation on the skin during early storage which is the main cause of bacterial contamination of processing line during filleting. First results have shown a slower bacterial deterioration leading to longer freshness period and shelf life extension. Reduction in *L. monocytogenes* on spiked skin cod has also been observed, as influenced by the ChitoClear® chitosan coating types (Lauzon *et al.* 2012). This is an important finding since raw fish is being used in refrigerated ready-to-eat products, such as cold-smoked fish, carpaccio and sushi products.

Based on these findings, the evaluation of different chitosan coatings for the fishery industry was conducted in collaboration with Fjarðalax ehf (gutted salmon) and Rammi hf (whole, raw shrimp and gutted cod to be processed into fillets). The results of the shelf life studies conducted on these three fishery products are presented in this report.

2. MATERIAL & METHODS

2.1 Treatment of raw fishery products with chitosan

Application of chitosan treatment was tested at Fjarðalax after salmon gutting and rinsing shortly after slaughter, prior to packaging, and on board the vessel Múlaberg (Rammi), for shrimp that had been pre-cleaned and graded and for whole cod newly gutted and rinsed, obtained as a by-catch. Shelf life studies were conducted for these three fishery products.

2.1.1 Trial 1: Whole, gutted salmon

The aim of the study was to evaluate the functionality of three chitosan concentrations (B-C-D), assessing their antimicrobial properties and ability to extend the shelf life of newly slaughtered and gutted salmon.

Whole salmon (n=2 x 6 fish) slaughtered late on October 28th, 2013, were treated the following morning with three different chitosan solutions (denoted B, C and D, 10 L each), by dipping a fish for 1 min into the solution and allowing excess solution to run off for about 1 min. One group was left untreated as control (n=2 x 6 fish), resulting in four groups in total.

Sample code	Chitosan treatment	pH of solution	Viscosity of solution (cP)
K-L	Untreated	-	-
B-L	B	4.4	490
C-L	C	4.5	1140
D-L	D	4.8	1936

cP, centipoise

Six fish were packed per expanded polystyrene (EPS) box with two cooling mats set on top on the fish and one temperature logger (iButton DS1922L, Maxim Integrated Products, Inc., USA) inserted in one fish in each box. In addition, one logger was set on the outside wall of one box for each treatment to monitor the ambient temperature at 10-min intervals. The logger accuracy was of +/- 0.5°C, with a resolution of 0.0625°C. All the boxes were identified, assembled on a pallet and shipped to Reykjavík overnight, delivered to Matís the following

morning. Upon arrival the boxes were stored in a cooling chamber at a mean storage temperature of $+1.5 \pm 0.4^{\circ}\text{C}$. Sampling was performed on days 3-6-10-14 and 17. Digital photography was taken for each sample treatment on each sampling day.

For microbial analysis, salmon skin (12.5 cm^2 obtained from two pieces, one close to the head and the other towards the tail) was aseptically sampled in duplicate, using two fish randomly taken from two boxes. Skin samples were diluted with 125 ml of cooled Maximum Recovery Diluent (MRD, Oxoid) and stomached for 1 min. Serial dilution was performed as required and aliquots plated onto modified Iron agar (17°C , 5-7 days; modified from Gram *et al.* 1987 with 1% NaCl and no overlay) for total psychrotrophic viable counts (TVC) and H_2S -producing bacteria (black colonies), and onto CFC medium (22°C , 3 days) modified according to Stanbridge and Board (1994) to enumerate presumptive pseudomonads, counting pink colonies. The detection limit was 20 colony-forming units (CFU)/ cm^2 of skin samples. Estimation of *Photobacterium phosphoreum* (Pp) counts was achieved by qPCR method developed at Matís (E. Reynisson, unpublished). Briefly, 1 ml of the 10-fold diluted skin sample in MRD buffer was frozen at -20°C for later DNA extraction. For the DNA extraction, the diluted samples were centrifuged at $11.000 \times g$ for 5 min to form a pellet. The supernatant was discarded and DNA was recovered from the pellet using thermal HotShot DNA extraction method (Truett *et al.* 2000). All PCR reactions were done using the MX 3005p instrument. The PCR was done using Universal Mastermix (Applied Biosystems). Primers were synthesized and purified with HPLC (MWG, Ebersberg, Germany). The DNA standard used for quantification of *P. phosphoreum* was previously calibrated against the PPDM-Malthus conductance method (Dalgaard *et al.* 1996; Lauzon 2003) using fish samples from storage trials.

Determination of flesh pH was done with a pH electrode (SE 1004 Mettler Toledo GmbH, Greifensee, die Schweiz) connected to a Knick pH meter (Portames 913 pH, Knick, Berlin, Germany). After calibration at pH 4 and 7, the electrode was stabbed into the flesh where the skin had been removed at two positions (towards the head and the tail). All results are presented as an average of two replicate samples. Microbiological data are expressed as \log_{10} CFU/g. Statistical analysis of data was done using NCSS 2000 (NCSS, Utah, USA) to carry out an analysis of variance. Comparison of data with respect to treatments at each sampling day was done using the Fisher's LSD multiple comparison test. The threshold level for significance was 0.05.

The rest of the fish (2 fillets per fish) was used for sensory evaluation. TVB-N content of pooled minced flesh samples (one per treatment) was evaluated on days 10, 14 and 17 using fillet pieces remaining of the sensory evaluation. The method of Malle and Tao (1987) was used and performed by the chemical analysis laboratory at Matís.

Sensory evaluation aimed to assess differences in quality deterioration and shelf life as well as the effect of the treatments on sensory characteristics. Generic Descriptive Analysis (GDA), as introduced by Lawless and Heymann (2010), was used to assess cooked samples (described in **Appendix I**). Thirteen panelists participated in the sensory evaluation, eight to eleven in each session. They had all been trained according to international standards (ISO 8586, 1993); including detection and recognition of tastes and odors, use of scales, and in the development and use of descriptors. The members of the panel were experienced in using the sensory methods selected. The panel was trained in recognition of sensory

characteristics of the samples and describing the intensity of each attribute for a given sample using an unstructured scale (from 0 to 100). Most of the attributes were defined and described by the sensory panel during other projects. The sensory attributes were 27 (**Appendix I**). Portions weighing about 40 g were cut and placed in aluminium boxes coded with three-digit numbers. The samples were cooked for 6 min in a pre-warmed oven (Convotherm Elektrogeräte GmbH, Eglfing, Germany) at 95-100°C with air circulation and steam, and then served warm to the panel. Each panelist evaluated duplicates of each test group in a random order in ten sessions. Four panelists did not taste one or more samples on day seventeen. A computerized system (FIZZ, Version 2.0, 1994-2000, Biosystèmes) was used for data recording. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was carried out in the statistical program NCSS 2000 on GDA data. Comparison of data with respect to treatments was performed using the Duncan's multiple comparison test. Significance level was set at 5%.

2.1.2 Trial 2: Whole, raw shrimp

This study evaluated the functionality of two chitosan concentrations assessing their antimicrobial properties and ability to extend the shelf life of whole shrimp. The selection of treatments was based on a previous shrimp trial conducted at a laboratory scale in 2012. Newly caught, whole shrimp that had been sorted and ready for bulk storage, were treated on board the fishing vessel Múlaberg with two different chitosan solutions (denoted A and B, 10 L each) and compared to untreated shrimp (K) similarly packaged (2 kg in plastic bag) in EPS boxes. Treated shrimp (2-kg portions) were put in a basket and dipped for 1 min in a chitosan solution, drained and transferred aseptically to a bag then stored in EPS box with ice, repeating the treatment to prepare 4 boxes for each group. Four portions of untreated shrimp were prepared as the control group. Upon landing (almost 4 days post-catch), temperature loggers (iButton DS1922L) were inserted in 6 boxes (2 per group) that were shipped overnight to the laboratory (Matís) for raw product analysis. Further, one logger was set on the outside wall of one box for each group to monitor the ambient temperature at 10-min intervals. The other 6 boxes were used for the evaluation of cooked, peeled shrimp, produced 6 days post-catch and stored frozen for 2 months until analysed by sensory methods. At Matís, the raw shrimp boxes were received and analysed 5 days post-catch (1 box per group) and the rest stored refrigerated for 3 more days until analysed.

Sample code	Chitosan treatment	pH of solution	Viscosity of solution (cP)
K	untreated	-	-
A	A	4.26	317
B	B	4.40	601

cP, centipoise

Raw shrimp were subjected to sensory analysis (triplicate samples, 3 x 10 individuals) and microbial analysis was performed on duplicate samples (per group) on days 5 and 8 post-catch, enumerating for total psychrotrophic viable microbiota (TVC), H₂S-producing bacteria and pseudomonads as described earlier. Whole individuals (n=25) were minced as one pooled sample. A tenfold dilution was prepared using 20 g minced shrimp and 180 g cooled MRD, stomached for 1 min. Serial dilution was performed as required and aliquots plated and cultivated as described earlier. Determination of pH was performed on days 5 and 8 in

about 5 g of minced shrimp diluted in 5 ml deionised water at room temperature, using the Radiometer PHM 80 (Radiometer Analytical A/S, Bagsvaerd, Denmark). The pH meter had been calibrated using the buffer solutions of pH 7.00 +/- 0.01 and 4.01 +/- 0.01 (25°C). The rest of the microbiological minced samples was analysed for TVB-N content. Digital photography was taken for each sample treatment on each sampling day.

Raw shrimp were evaluated with the Quality Index Method (Martinsdóttir 1995), as described in **Appendix II**. Samples were evaluated by nine panelists on day five and seven panelists on day eight. They were also evaluated with an industrial freshness score sheet for raw shrimp. One sample of raw shrimp counted 10 individuals presented on a white plastic board. Each sample was coded with a three-digit random number and presented to the panelists in a random order. All treatments were evaluated in triplicate on every sampling day. The panelists evaluated the samples individually using a sheet with the QI scale. The statistical program NCSS 2000 was used to calculate analysis of variance (ANOVA, General Linear Model and One Way ANOVA) to compare sample groups and calculate *p*-values. Duncan's test was used to calculate multiple comparisons between sample groups. The significance level was set at 5%. Comparison of microbial and chemical data was performed using the Fisher's LSD multiple comparison test.

Sensory evaluation was also carried out on three sample groups of cooked, peeled shrimp. The main purpose of the experiment was to evaluate the effect of post-catch treatments with chitosan solutions of different concentrations on the sensory characteristics of precooked shrimp processed 6 days post-catch and stored frozen for 2 months at Rammi hf. All panelists who participated in this project had been trained according to international standards (ISO 8586, 1993), as described earlier. The panel was trained in recognition of the sensory characteristics of the samples and describing the intensity of each attribute for a given sample using an unstructured scale (from 0 to 100). After thawing, the shrimps were served at temperature 10-15°C to the panelists. Each sample contained ~10 shrimps presented in an aluminium box with a lid. A computerized system (FIZZ) was used for data recording. All samples were coded with three-digit numbers and presented to the panel in a random order. Each panelist evaluated duplicates of each sample group. Samples of precooked shrimp were evaluated with Generic Descriptive Analysis (GDA) of 22 attributes.

The GDA scale for precooked shrimp was developed in earlier projects. The panel had one training session where the scale was reviewed with a fresh control sample from production and group B as references. The scale was adjusted to the references and the use of the scale synchronized among the panelists. The scale is shown in **Appendix II**. Samples were evaluated by seven panelists. The statistical program NCSS 2000 was used to calculate analysis of variance (ANOVA, General Linear Model) to compare sample groups and calculate *p*-values. Duncan's test was used to calculate multiple comparisons between sample groups and significance level set at 5%.

2.1.3 Trial 3: Whole, gutted cod and its products

This study evaluated the functionality of two chitosan concentrations, assessing their antimicrobial properties and ability to extend the shelf life of whole cod and their products. The selection of treatments was based on whole fish trials conducted earlier. Freshly caught and gutted cod (n=2 x 32) were treated (30.08.2014) on board the vessel Múlaberg (Rammi)

with two different chitosan solutions (denoted C and D, 30 L each) by dipping a fish for 1 min into the solution and allowing excess solution to run off for about 1 min. One group was left untreated as control (n=32), resulting in three groups in total. Each group was stored in a tub and fish iced as usual. Upon landing, the tubs were shipped for processing to Þorlákshöfn. Three days post-catch, 4 fish per group were transferred to EPS boxes (23-kg size) and one temperature logger introduced into a bottom fish in each box along with one logger stuck onto the surface of the boxes to monitor environmental conditions at 10-min intervals. On the same day, 16 fish from each group were processed into loins. Beheading and filleting was done while older fish was being processed but deskinning was done mechanically in a different processing line, starting with group D, then C and finally K (control, untreated). Loins were trimmed and eight pieces packed into EPS boxes, 4 per group, to be analysed 3, 7, 10 and 13 days post-processing. Temperature loggers were inserted at mid position in one box per group and one logger was also stuck onto the wall surface of the 3 selected boxes intended as the last sampling point. The rest of the fish in tubs were stored in the storage room chilled until processed 3 days later. A logger was also inserted in a fish in each tub. All boxes were identified (K1, C1, D1, referring to lot 1) and shipped to Mátis for refrigerated storage until the end of shelf life.

Sample code	Chitosan treatment	pH of solution	Viscosity of solution (cP)
K	untreated	-	-
C	C	4.70	1028
D	D	4.96	2168

cP, centipoise

Six days post-catch, 12 fish from each group were processed into loins. Beheading, filleting and deskinning were done mechanically in an unused processing line, starting with group D, then C and finally K (control, untreated). Loins were trimmed and eight pieces packed into EPS boxes, 3 per group, to be analysed 3, 6 and 10 days post-processing. Temperature loggers were inserted at mid position in one box per group and one logger was also stuck onto the wall surface of the 3 selected boxes intended as the last sampling point. All boxes were identified (K2, C2, D2, referring to lot 2) and shipped to Mátis for refrigerated storage until the end of shelf life.

At each sampling day, two loins were minced and used for microbial and chemical analysis (pH and TVB-N), while six loins were used for sensory evaluation. TVB-N content was only measured at selected sampling days. In addition, whole fish were examined on days 3 and 6 post-catch. Skin samples (12,5 cm² obtained from head and tail area of one fish, as one sample) were aseptically removed, subjected to tenfold dilution and stomaching before microbial analysis, enumerating for total psychrotrophic viable microbiota (TVC), H₂S-producing bacteria and pseudomonads as described earlier. Duplicate samples were analysed. Determination of flesh pH on whole fish was done with a pH electrode (SE 1004 Mettler Toledo GmbH) connected to a Knick pH meter (Portames 913 pH). After calibration at pH 4 and 7, the electrode was stabbed into the flesh where the skin had been removed at two positions (towards the head and the tail). The rest of the fish (2 fillets per fish) was used for sensory evaluation. Digital photography of whole fish was taken for each sample treatment on each sampling day.

Two lots of cod loins, including three groups each, were evaluated with sensory evaluation for up to 10 days of storage. The main purpose was to evaluate differences in quality deterioration and shelf life according to sensory evaluation by a trained panel. Generic Descriptive Analysis and Torry freshness score sheet (Shewan *et al.* 1953) were used to assess cooked samples (**Appendix III**). Thirteen panelists participated in the sensory evaluation. They had all been trained according to international standards as described earlier. The members of the panel were experienced in using the GDA method and Torry freshness score sheet for cod. The intensity of each attribute for a given sample was evaluated using a 15 cm unstructured scale which in analysis was transformed to numbers from 0 to 100. Most of the attributes were defined and described by the sensory panel during earlier projects. The sensory attributes were 26 and are described in **Appendix III**.

Portions weighing about 40 g were cut from the cod loins and placed in aluminium boxes coded with three-digit random numbers. The samples were cooked for 6 min in a pre-warmed oven (Convotherm Elektrogeräte GmbH) at 95-100°C with air circulation and steam, and then served warm to the panel. Each panelist evaluated duplicates of each test group in a random order (maximum four samples per session). A computerised system (FIZZ) was used for data recording.

The sensory evaluation program Panelcheck V1.3.2 (Nofima, Tromsø, Norway) was used to assess panel performance. The programs NCSS 2000 and Microsoft Excel 2007 were used for statistical analysis of the results. Analysis of variance (ANOVA, General linear model method) and Duncan's test was used to perform multiple comparisons on GDA data. Difference between the panelists' use of the scale was corrected for. One Way ANOVA was used for statistical analysis of Torry data. The significance level was set at 5%.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1 Shelf life trials

Based on the preliminary trials conducted in a previous project, a chitosan product prepared into solutions showed mainly antibacterial effects towards fish spoilage bacteria, especially *P. phosphoreum*, H₂S-producing bacteria and to a lesser extent pseudomonads. Effect to the overall fish microbiota (TVC) was the least observed. In this project, the effects of chitosan solutions, of different concentrations, on different products (of different pH and nature) were assessed during three storage trials. The aim was to evaluate whether the extension of freshness period and sensory shelf life of fish products could be achieved, as observed in laboratory trials, when used in field experiments on board a fishing vessel or at a fish processing facility shelf life.

3.1.1 Trial 1: Whole, gutted salmon

Newly slaughtered salmon, gutted and rinsed, were treated with 3 chitosan solutions before packaging. Temperature monitoring of whole fish from packaging till the end of storage is illustrated in **Figure 1. Table 1** provides initial fish temperature and mean product temperature. Differences were observed in the raw material temperature, being either just below 2.5°C or just above 3.5°C at packaging. Nevertheless appropriate cooling was applied

early storage, which resulted in similar mean product temperatures over the storage period. Mean ambient storage temperature was $+1.4 \pm 0.4^\circ\text{C}$ over the period studied.

Table 1. Initial fish temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$) at packaging and mean product temperature during storage period of 17 days (including standard deviation; $n=2$)

Treatment	Control	Group B	Group C	Group D
Initial product T ($^\circ\text{C}$)	2.4	2.2	3.9	3.5
SD	0.9	0.4	0.1	0.4
Mean product T ($^\circ\text{C}$)	1.5	1.4	1.4	1.4
SD	0.5	0.3	0.2	0.3

Figure 1. Fish temperature ($^\circ\text{C}$) in EPS boxes from packaging to the end of storage

Freshness deterioration was evaluated by scheme (**Appendix I**) of cooked salmon samples at regular intervals. Results are shown in **Appendix IV**. Quality deterioration of salmon is first characterized by the initial loss of the fresh fish flavor (sweet, metallic, fresh fish oil), which is followed by the development of off-odors and off-flavors. End of shelf life is usually determined when sensory attributes related to spoilage such as sour, rancid, queasy sweet, putrid odor and/or flavor become evident. Descriptive profiling methods such as generic descriptive analysis (GDA) and quantitative descriptive analysis (QDA[®]), described by Stone and Sidel (2004), are commonly used to describe the sensory characteristics of products. These methods may be used to provide a detailed quantitative description of product's sensory characteristics, i.e. appearance, odor, flavor and texture. Each attribute is evaluated on an unstructured scale (0 to 100). During the first few days after catch or slaughter, the average GDA score for sweet flavor of salmon is usually above 40. When the sensory score referred to as GDA score is around 30, the sweet flavor is still characteristic for the fish, but when the score has decreased to a score below 20-25, it indicates that the sweet flavor is no longer evident and the freshness period terminated. When the average GDA score for spoilage related attributes such as sour, rancid and queasy sweet odor and/or flavor is above 20 (on the scale 0 to 100), most panelists detect them, which indicates that the sample has reached the end of shelf life.

Sensory analysis indicated that few spoilage attributes were noticeable 14 days post-slaughter (rancid flavor) while characteristic freshness attributes had considerably faded

after 12-13 days (score <25). At day 17, freshness parameters had dropped to a score of ~10 (sweet, metallic and fresh fish oil flavor/odor) and several negative parameters had surpassed a score of 20 (sour and putrid odor, queasy flavor) or were approaching this limit (queasy odor, sour/rancid flavor). **This suggests that the shelf life of the untreated salmon was about 17 days at +1.5 °C.** These changes corresponded to a slowdown in growth of bacterial groups, reaching a certain maximal level around day 17 (**Figure 2**). Total viable psychrotrophic microbial counts (TVC) and pseudomonad counts on skin surface were close to 10^9 cfu/cm², while lower levels of H₂S-producing bacteria (10^8 cfu/cm²) and *P. phosphoreum* (Pp almost 10^7 cfu/cm²) were detected. The little TVB-N increase (12%) observed between days 10-17 is reflected by this lower level of spoilage bacteria (Pp) on the skin and a slow flesh pH increase (**Figure 3**).

Figure 2. Microbiological load on the skin of untreated gutted salmon stored at +1.5°C for 17 days

Figure 3. Changes in pH of flesh on fish at tail and head positions during chilled storage

The chitosan treatments did not apparently affect the quality parameters of salmon, except for the significantly higher scores obtained in C-treated fish on day 3 (earthy odor and rancid

odor/flavor) compared to the control. **Figure 4** illustrates five of the attributes evaluated, based on odor (sweet and metallic) and flavor (sweet, metallic and fresh oil) relating to freshness characteristics. Sweet odor and flavor scored highest in all groups during the first 10 days of storage, after which a rapid deterioration was observed in the untreated group (control) compared to the other treatments. Freshness characteristics of the untreated fish were completely lost 14 days post-slaughter, while the sweet flavor was better maintained in the chitosan-treated fish, especially when used at higher concentrations (groups C & D). At day 17, the sweet and metallic odor scores of group D were significantly higher than in untreated fish, while only marginal significance was observed for sweet and fresh oil flavors in these groups.

Figure 4. GDA scores of selected freshness characteristics attributes for odor (O-) and flavor (F-) in cooked salmon samples evaluated during the 17-day storage period

Spoilage attributes (**Figure 5**) of the control group had reached significantly higher levels on day 17 compared to all other chitosan treatments (queasy odor) or groups C & D (putrid odor). Further group C had significantly less sour odor than the control, while group D had significantly (marginal) less sour flavor than the control. Overall, the control fish had reached the rejection level (score 20) for important spoilage attributes (sour/queasy odor/flavor and putrid odor) on day 17. The spoilage characteristics were developing more slowly in the

chitosan treatments, with group D being the most delayed and group B the most advanced. Comparing the score of spoilage attributes for the chitosan treatments on day 17 to those of the control, it can be estimated that the chitosan treatments had delayed spoilage by about one (group B), two (group C) and three (group D) days. Freshness extension was less evident, but some sweet flavor was still detectable on day 17 in groups C and D, corresponding to the sweetness of the control fish on day 13 (estimated from the curve). Overall, it can be estimated that the shelf life of the treated fish would have reached at least 18 (B), 19 (C) and 20 (D) days at +1.4°C. Digital photographs taken at sampling are shown in **Appendix V**.

Figure 5. GDA scores of selected spoilage characteristics attributes for odor (O-) and flavor (F-) in cooked salmon samples evaluated during the 17-day storage period

The effect of the chitosan treatments on the developing microbiota of salmon skin over the 17-day storage period is shown in **Figure 6**. Overall, it is observed that the antibacterial effect of chitosan treatments differs among the bacterial group investigated. The least effect was observed towards pseudomonads, the dominating spoilage group in this trial, while the most affected spoilage bacteria were *P. phosphoreum*, for which growth was delayed for at least 10 day (below detection limit). Generally, all chitosan treatments delayed pseudomonad growth to some extent (ca 10 to 100-fold), but group D provided the greatest effect, which was of statistical significance on days 6, 14 and 17 compared to untreated fish.

In fact, comparison of pseudomonad counts for untreated (day 10) and group D (day 17) fish revealed a growth delay of one week. Growth of H₂S-producing bacteria was significantly delayed by at least one week for all chitosan treatments when compared to the control microbial load on day 10, with group D resulting in the slowest proliferation. For the most sensitive bacterial group, *P. phosphoreum*, growth was hardly detected in group D while some growth was detected in groups B and C on days 14 and 17 (a 1,000 to 10,000-fold reduction in counts compared to control). These counts were significantly lower than those of untreated fish from day 6.

Figure 6. Microbial growth (CFU/cm²) on the salmon skin of untreated (control) and chitosan-treated (groups B-C-D) fish during the 17-day storage period at +1.4°C. TVC, total viable psychrotrophic counts; and counts of specific spoilage bacteria (H₂S-producing bacteria, pseudomonads and *Photobacterium phosphoreum*). Different letters indicate a significant difference between groups. A black asterisk means a treatment sample is significantly different to control, while a red asterisk to all other treatments.

Figure 7. TVB-N content of flesh samples of untreated (control) and chitosan-treated (groups B-C-D) fish during the 17-day storage period at +1.4°C.

Changes in chemical parameters were evaluated in the flesh; pH was measured at two positions on 2 fish at each sampling day while TVB-N was evaluated at late storage in pooled samples obtained from the remaining samples of the sensory samples for each group. A little increase (12%) in TVB-N was observed in control fish between days 10-17, corresponding to the slow flesh pH increase. Similar data were obtained for treated fish (**Figure 7**). This little increase in TVB-N indicates that it is not an appropriate indicator for salmon spoilage. Changes in pH (**Figure 8**) were minimal and not influenced by the chitosan treatments

Figure 8. Changes in flesh pH underneath the salmon skin towards the head and tail of untreated (control) and chitosan-treated (groups B-C-D) fish during the 17-day storage period at +1.4°C. A black asterisk means a treatment sample is significantly different to control.

Conclusion

The storage trial indicated that the shelf life of salmon slaughtered late on October 28th and packaged the following morning was 17 days for a fish mean temperature of $1.5 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Freshness characteristics were lost after 14 days of storage. Chitosan treatments by dipping the whole, gutted fish for 1 min in a chitosan solution resulted in some freshness (at least 4 days) and shelf life extension, increasing with increasing chitosan concentrations. Solutions C or D would be the recommended treatment to ensure enhanced freshness and reduced microbial growth. In earlier studies, chitosan treatment has also been shown to reduce *Listeria* contamination on the skin of fish and may be used to ensure safety of the resulting salmon products when eaten raw or smoked.

3.1.2 Trial 2: Raw shrimp

This trial evaluated the effects of two chitosan concentrations on the sensory, chemical and microbial changes of newly caught, raw shrimp treated on board and stored for up to 8 days post-treatment. Further sensory evaluation of cooked, peeled shrimp, produced 6 days post-catch from previously treated shrimp, was performed 2 months post-freezing and compared to a reference (untreated on board) sample to assess the quality changes or possibly defects the chitosan treatments may have incurred to the finished product.

Temperature monitoring of whole shrimp started after landing when the boxes were retrieved till the end of storage as shown in **Figure 9**. **Table 2** provides mean product and ambient temperatures. Differences were observed in shrimp mean temperature, despite similar cooling procedures, which could be partly explained by the variable ambient temperature as well as faster spoilage in control group with heat being generated by microbial metabolism.

Table 2. Mean shrimp and ambient temperature (°C) during storage (n=2)

Treatment	Control	Group A	Group B	Ambient
Mean product T (°C)	1.0	0.3	0.0	1.3
SD	0.5	0.5	0.3	2.3

Figure 9. Shrimp temperature (°C) in EPS boxes from landing to the end of storage. Temperature peak at almost day 5 occurred due to sampling from the boxes.

The sensory quality of the raw shrimp was evaluated with the Quality Index Method as well as with a commercial freshness scale. The results are summarised in **Table 3**. No significant difference was seen in the freshness score during the storage time. All groups received a score around 3 (moderate quality) on day five and scores between 2 and 3 on day eight, with the control group receiving the lowest score (2 = borderline) i.e. lowest quality. No difference was seen in QI scores for odor or total Quality Index between groups during the storage time. The results indicate a difference in color on day eight with the control group receiving a higher QI score, meaning worse color than the other two groups. A difference

was also seen in darkness of head and roe color. Group B had the fewest shrimp with dark colored heads on both days five and eight, but the control group had less discolored or dark roe than other groups. The results therefore indicate that the chitosan solutions reduced the dark color formation in the heads and shells of the shrimp but increased the dark color of the roe. Digital photographs taken 5 days post-catch are shown in **Appendix VI**.

Table 3. Mean values for Quality Index scores and freshness scores

	Head	Colour	Odour	Eggs	QIM index	Freshness score
Day 5						
A	1,8 ± 0,8 a	1,4 ± 0,5	1,0 ± 0,7	0,6 ± 0,8 a	4,8 ± 1,6	3,0 ± 0,5
B	1,2 ± 0,6 b	1,4 ± 0,6	0,9 ± 0,9	0,4 ± 0,7	3,9 ± 2,1	3,2 ± 0,9
K	2,0 ± 0,6 a	1,6 ± 0,6	1,1 ± 0,5	0,1 ± 0,3 b	4,7 ± 1,3	3,1 ± 0,6
p-value	0,001	0,399	0,446	0,023	0,102	0,582
Day 8						
A	2,3 ± 0,6 a	1,5 ± 0,5 b	1,7 ± 1,0	0,8 ± 0,7 a	6,3 ± 1,7	2,7 ± 0,8
B	1,9 ± 0,5 b	1,6 ± 0,5 b	1,7 ± 0,7	1,0 ± 0,8 a	6,2 ± 1,6	2,6 ± 0,7
K	2,1 ± 0,6	2,0 ± 0,7 a	1,8 ± 0,8	0,3 ± 0,4 b	6,1 ± 1,6	2,2 ± 0,7
p-value	0,048	0,003	0,822	0,002	0,877	0,238

Different letters indicate significant difference among the treatments for each parameter and sampling day
 QIM index: 0 = very fresh, 11= very spoiled. Freshness score: 5 = very fresh, 1 = unfit for consumption.

Figure 10 presents the microbiological data obtained during the evaluation of whole shrimp, including the gut. No difference was observed between the groups which could be explained by the chitosan surface treatment of shrimp not affecting the gut microbiota, most likely to be an important contributor to the overall shrimp microbial load.

Figure 10. Development of psychrotrophic microbiota (TVC, 17 °C) and spoilage bacteria (H₂S-producing bacteria and pseudomonads) during refrigerated storage of untreated (control) and

chitosan-treated whole shrimp. Mean values (n=2) with SD (error bars) are shown; ns indicates that no significant difference was observed between treatments at each respective sampling day (p<0.05).

Figure 11 also shows that little difference was seen in TVB-N formation among the different groups, resulting in similar pH development. It is noteworthy that an earlier trial conducted on shrimp 2 days post-catch did show some effects of chitosan treatments on spoilage bacteria, resulting in slower TVB-N formation in treated shrimp, which was not observed here. This could be due to a better controlled and lower environmental temperature in the earlier trial ($0.5 \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$) compared to this one.

Figure 11. Total volatile base nitrogen (TVB-N) content (left) and pH measurements (right) in untreated (control) and chitosan-treated whole shrimp. Mean values (n=2) are shown, with SD (error bars); ns indicates that no significant difference was observed between treatments at each respective sampling day (p<0.05).

Another part of the study included the sensory evaluation of cooked, peeled shrimp, produced 6 days post-catch from previously treated shrimp, testing 2 months post-freezing and comparing to a reference shrimp sample. Rather small differences were detected between the untreated and treated groups of shrimp that had been cooked and peeled (**Table 4**). No difference was seen in odor. A clear difference was detected in red color of the membrane surrounding the shrimp. Group B had a more red membrane than the other two groups. No clear difference was seen between groups in flavor, but difference in metallic flavor was marginally significant where group A had the most metallic flavor but group K the least. A difference was also seen in texture where group B was evaluated mushier than the other two groups. All groups were characterized by decreasing freshness but no spoilage was detected. Freshness characteristics; sweet and shellfish odor/flavor were of moderate strength and an obvious metallic flavor was detected. The texture was moderately soft, juicy and tender, rather springy and neither mushy nor crumbly.

Table 4. Mean values of GDA sensory attributes for cooked and peeled shrimp prepared from untreated (K) and treated (A, B) whole shrimp. Different letters within a line indicate a statistical difference between groups.

Sensory attribute	K	A	B	p-value
O-sweet	30	33	37	0.237
O-shellfish	28	27	30	0.754
O-vanilla	2	2	1	0.565
O-TMA	1	1	0	0.520
O-sour	4	5	3	0.565
O-sulfur	0	0	0	0.675
A-red	45	b 48	b 55	a 0.001
A-color	22	21	20	0.593
F-sweet	42	44	40	0.580
F-metallic	19	24	18	0.088
F-shellfish	31	29	26	0.307
F-pungent	5	6	6	0.780
F-sour	2	a 1	0	b 0.037
F-TMA	1	1	0	0.848
F-putrid	0	1	1	0.855
F-off	7	7	10	0.577
T-soft	43	43	42	0.949
T-springy	40	38	39	0.872
T-juicy	60	58	53	0.133
T-tender	60	61	59	0.705
T-mushy	18	b 18	b 26	a 0.033
T-crumbly	16	17	22	0.124

Conclusion

For cooked and peeled shrimp, small differences were seen between groups. No difference was seen between the control group and group A which was treated with the less concentrated solution of chitosan. Treatment with a stronger solution of chitosan resulted in a redder membrane surrounding the shrimp and a more mushy texture. All groups were characterised by decreasing freshness but no spoilage was detected. Similarly, little difference was observed among raw shrimp treatments, except for the blackening of head and shell being retarded due to chitosan treatments while roe discoloration was enhanced.

3.1.3 Trial 3: Whole, gutted cod and its products

This trial evaluated the functionality of two chitosan concentrations, C and D, assessing their antimicrobial properties and ability to extend the shelf life of whole cod and its filleted products. **Tables 5** and **6** summarise the temperature data collected over the storage trial. **Figures 12** to **15** illustrate the temperature variations observed from raw material reception, after processing and until end of storage trial.

Table 5. Mean ambient temperature (°C) from packaging in EPS boxes till end of storage period (including standard deviation; n=2)

Treatments	Whole cod in EPS		Loins– lot 1		Loins– lot 2	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
K	0.1	1.1	-0.6	0.8	-0.2	0.9
C	0.3	0.9	-0.7	0.8	-0.4	0.9
D	0.4	0.9	-0.7	0.9	0.2	0.9
Mean T	0.3	1.0	-0.7	0.8	-0.1	0.9

Table 6. Mean fish temperature (°C) during storage period (including standard deviation; n=2)

Treatments	Whole cod in tubs		Whole cod in EPS		Loins – lot 1		Loins – lot 2	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
K	2.6	1.7	-0.3	0.2	-0.1	0.7	0.1	1.0
C	NA	NA	-0.1	0.5	-0.3	0.7	0.1	0.9
D	1.9	0.9	-0.2	0.1	-0.1	0.5	0.2	0.8
Mean T			-0.2	0.3	-0.2	0.6	0.2	0.9

Temperature of whole cod after reception at the processing site is shown in **Figure 13**, ranging from about 0.5-2°C. Rapid chilling occurred upon storage in EPS boxes at Matís, resulting in a steady mean fish temperature. On the other hand, temperature of whole cod at the processing site for 3 days was unstable and increased rapidly after one day of storage. Most likely the ambient temperature was higher and ice melted rapidly. This resulted in a mean fish temperature of about +2°C in tubs compared to -0.2°C in EPS boxes (**Figure 12**).

Figure 12. Mean fish temperature (°C) in EPS boxes (left) and ambient temperature from packaging till the end of storage

Figure 13. Temperature (°C) of whole, gutted cod in tubs stored at processing site

Figure 14. Ambient temperature (left) and fish temperature in EPS boxes (lot 1, right) from packaging till the end of storage

Figure 15. Ambient temperature (left) and fish temperature in EPS boxes (lot 2, right) from packaging till the end of storage

Sensory evaluation of cooked cod was performed by two methods; Torry freshness assessment and GDA method describing 26 attributes relating to odor, appearance, flavor and texture. Freshness loss is generally characterised by a Torry score of 7 (out of 10, see **Appendix I**) and GDA freshness attributes approaching a value of 25-30% (sweet and shellfish odor; sweet and metallic flavor). End of shelf life is usually determined when sensory attributes related to spoilage such as sour, pungent, TMA odor and/or flavor become evident (>20%). When the average Torry score is around 5.5, most panelists detect those attributes, which indicates that the sample is approaching the end of shelf life (Martinsdóttir *et al.* 2001).

Whole fish was evaluated on day 3 and day 6 from catch. On day 3, the control group had more metallic flavor than other groups and group C had a firmer texture than the control group and group D (**Table A, Appendix VII**). On day 6 post-catch, group D received higher scores than the control group and group C for sweet flavor which is an attribute characteristic for fresh cod. Group D also received a lower score for potato odor than the control group and was evaluated lighter and more heterogeneous in colour and with less mushy texture than group C. Group D had a firmer texture than the other two groups.

Digital photographs of whole fish, stored in tubs and processed into loins, were taken prior to processing on days 3 and 6 post-catch and are shown in **Appendix VIII**. **Fish in lot 1** was filleted 3 days post-catch and evaluated on days 3, 7 and 10 post-processing (or 6, 10 and 13 days post-catch). Not much difference was seen after 3 days of storage (**Table B, Appendix VII**). Group C1 had a firmer texture than group D1 and a more rubbery texture than the other two groups. On day 7 from filleting, the control group had less dishcloth odor than groups C1 and D1, and a less heterogeneous colour than group C1. On day 10, group C1 had more potato odor than D1 and a lighter colour than the control group. Three panelists did not evaluate flavor and texture of one or more samples due to a strong spoilage odor. Since only three panelists evaluated flavor and texture attributes on day ten, these attributes are not included in the results.

Fish in lot 2 was filleted on day 6 post-catch and evaluated on days 3 and 6 post-processing (9 and 12 days post-catch). Only minor differences were seen between groups with GDA (**Table C, Appendix VII**). Group C2 had a sweeter flavor than other groups on day 3 and a marginal significance was seen on day 6 for white precipitations and mushy texture where group C2 had the least precipitations, group D2 had the least mushy texture while the control group had the mushiest texture. Two panelists did not evaluate flavor and texture of one or more samples on storage day 6.

Torry results showed a marginally significant difference ($p = 0.09$) for whole fish on storage day 6 where group D had a higher Torry score than both group C and the control group (**Figure 16**). No significant differences in Torry scores were seen for lots 1 and 2.

Figure 16. Mean Torry freshness scores for cooked cod samples during storage (days post-catch). The green dashed line indicates loss of freshness (Torry score = 7) and the black dashed line indicates the fish is unfit for consumption (Torry score = 5.5). K, C and D stand for whole cod treatments while the indicative numbers 1 and 2 in the legend represent lots 1 and 2 for corresponding test groups.

Freshness characteristics determined by GDA were more apparent in group D than in the control group and group C on storage day 6 for whole fish. These results are supported with a higher Torry score for group D. No consistent differences were observed between groups in appearance or texture during the storage time and differences in odor and flavor were minor. Based on Torry score, fish in lot 1 had lost its freshness after 5 days post-processing (8 days post-catch) and was judged unfit for consumption after 7-8 days post-processing or 10-11 days post-catch. Control fish in lot 2 had a similar shelf life as for lot 1, while treated fish had one to two days longer shelf life as expected since this fish was filleted three days later. These results indicate that the chitosan treatment D prolonged the freshness period by about 2 days for whole fish stored at $0.3 \pm 1.0^{\circ}\text{C}$. The effect of the chitosan treatments after filleting was less evident and could be explained by the higher mean temperature ($1.9\text{-}2.6^{\circ}\text{C}$) of raw material during storage in tubs at the processing site prior to filleting. Nevertheless, the overall effect of chitosan skin treatment was greater after 6 days than 3 days.

Microbiological and physicochemical analyses of whole fish are presented in **Figures 17 to 20**. The results indicate the antibacterial effect of chitosan treatments on the skin of whole cod was greatest towards pseudomonads, among the bacterial groups evaluated, even though after being filleted. This is important since pseudomonads were found at higher levels than H_2S -producing bacteria in untreated fish. This antibacterial effect was significant at early storage time. For whole, treated fish, bacterial growth on skin was delayed by 3 days compared to the control (**Figure 17**). No significant difference was seen in flesh pH.

Figure 17. Development of psychrotrophic microbiota (TVC, 17 °C) and spoilage bacteria (H₂S-producing bacteria and pseudomonads) during refrigerated storage of untreated (control) and chitosan-treated whole cod. Changes in flesh pH are shown in the bottom right figure. Mean values (n=2) with SD (error bars) are shown; ns indicates that no significant difference was observed between treatments at each respective sampling day (p<0.05). Different letters indicate a significant difference between groups.

For loins prepared 3 days post-catch from treated fish, a significantly slower pseudomonad growth was seen, representing a 4-day delay compared to the control (**Figure 18**). Three days post-filleting, treatment D had a greater effect on the overall microbiota compared to control fish. For loins prepared 6 days post-catch and analysed 3 storage days, a significantly slower growth in H₂S-producing bacteria was seen in D-loins, while both C- and D-loins showed a significant slower growth of pseudomonads (**Figure 19**). No further antimicrobial effects were depicted after that storage time. This may be explained by the storage conditions of the 6-day post catch processed fish that had been stored at an undesirably high storage temperature at the processing site as shown in **Figure 13**.

Figure 18. Development of psychrotrophic microbiota (TVC, 17 °C) and spoilage bacteria (H₂S-producing bacteria and pseudomonads) during refrigerated storage of loins (lot 1) prepared 3 days post-catch (post-treatment) from untreated (control) and chitosan-treated whole cod. Changes in flesh pH are shown in the bottom right figure. Mean values (n=2) with SD (error bars) are shown; ns indicates that no significant difference was observed between treatments at each respective sampling day (p<0.05). Different letters indicate a significant difference between groups.

Figure 19. Development of psychrotrophic microbiota (TVC, 17 °C) and spoilage bacteria (H₂S-producing bacteria and pseudomonads) during refrigerated storage of loins (lot 2) prepared 6 days post-catch (post-treatment) from untreated (control) and chitosan-treated whole cod. Changes in pH are shown in the bottom right figure. Mean values (n=2) with SD (error bars) are shown; ns indicates that no significant difference was observed between treatments at each respective sampling day (p<0.05). Different letters indicate a significant difference between groups.

TVB-N content of loins prepared from chitosan-treated fish was not found to be significantly different from that of control fish (**Figure 20**). This can be explained for lot 1 by the little difference in quality changes obtained among the groups, demonstrated by the sensory data and the short lasting antibacterial effect of chitosan on skin after filleting. For lot 2, the undesirable fish temperature before filleting did not allow for the maintenance of quality parameters, but instead contributed to the rapid deterioration of all groups.

Figure 20. Total volatile base nitrogen (TVB-N) content in loins prepared from untreated (control) and chitosan-treated whole cod. Mean values (n=2) are shown, with SD (error bars). Different letters indicate a significant difference between groups ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

Skin treatments of whole, gutted cod with chitosan as a coating aimed to reduce surface contamination and promote enhanced quality of fish products. Freshness extension and delayed bacterial growth on skin was evidenced in whole cod after 6 days of storage, with characteristics as more sweet and firmer than control fish. For loins prepared from 3 and 6 days old treated cod, a slower microbial deterioration was only observed during early storage. Better chilling conditions may contribute to an enhanced effect of chitosan skin treatment as demonstrated by the results of whole cod stored at 0.3°C (EPS boxes) in contrast to 2°C (tubs).

4. CONCLUDING REMARKS

Chitosan has been shown to reduce bacterial load of fishery products. However, concentration, fish product pH and temperature will influence the extent of the antibacterial properties. Different chitosan treatments (A, B, C and D) were selected to evaluate their efficiency when used by fishery companies, aiming to reduce seafood surface contamination and promote enhanced quality of fishery products. The alkaline conditions establishing in chilled raw shrimp during storage (0-1°C) is the probable cause for no benefits of chitosan treatments A and B used shortly after catch, except for the slower blackening of head and shell observed compared to the control group. On the other hand, salmon treatments C and

D were most effective in significantly reducing skin bacterial load up to 6 days post-treatment (1.4°C) which inevitably contributed to the extended freshness period (by 4 days) and shelf life observed. Similarly, freshness extension and delayed bacterial growth on skin was evidenced in whole cod (-0.2°C) treated with solution D after 6 days of storage. For fish stored at higher temperature (2-3°C) and processed into loins on days 3 and 6 post-treatment (catch), a slower microbial deterioration was observed only during early storage of loins. The contribution of chitosan treatments to quality enhancement was not clearly demonstrated in these products. Based on the findings, better chilling conditions should contribute to an enhanced effect of chitosan skin treatment towards quality maintenance. Finally, in earlier studies chitosan treatment has also been shown to reduce *Listeria* contamination on the skin of fish and may be used to ensure safety of the resulting fish products when eaten raw or smoked.

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Appendix I – Sensory scale for cooked salmon

GDA sensory attributes for cooked salmon and their description

Sensory attribute	Short name	Scale	Definition
<i>ODOUR</i>			
sweet characteristic	O-sweet	none much	Sweet characteristic odour of boiled salmon
metallic	O-metallic	none much	Metallic odour
fresh oil	O-oil	none much	Fresh, unspoiled fish oil
acidic odour	O-acid	none much	Fresh sour, citric acid, not spoilage sour
earthy odour	O-earthy	none much	Earthy, mouldy odour
spoilage sour	O-sour	none much	Spoilage characteristic
rancid odour	O-rancid	none much	Rancid odour, spoilage characteristic
queasy sweet	O-queasy	none much	Queasy sweet, spoilage characteristic
putrid	O-putrid	none much	Putrid odour
<i>APPEARANCE</i>			
white precipitation	A-precipit.	none much	White precipitation on the surface and between flakes in the sample
heterogeneous colour	A-heterog.	none much	Surface of the sample, how heterogeneous is the colour.
colour	A-colour	white pink	Inside sample: How white / pink is the fish
yellow liquid	A-yellow l.	colourless yellow	How yellow is the liquid in the box
fat droplets	A-droplets	none much	Fat quantity in liquid surface
<i>FLAVOUR</i>			
sweet characteristic	F-sweet	none much	Sweet characteristic flavour of boiled salmon
metallic	F-metallic	none much	Metallic flavour
fresh oil	F-oil	none much	Flavour of fresh fish oil
acid flavour	F-acid	none much	Fresh sour, citric acid, not spoilage sour
earthy flavour	F-earthy	none much	Earthy / mouldy flavour
spoilage sour	F-sour	none much	Spoilage sour, spoilage characteristic
rancid flavour	F-rancid	none much	Rancid flavour, spoilage characteristic
queasy sweet	F-queasy	none much	Queasy sweet, spoilage characteristic
<i>TEXTURE</i>			
soft	T-soft	firm soft	Evaluated in first bite
juicy	T-juicy	dry juicy	Dry - draws liquid from the mouth
tender	T-tender	tough tender	Evaluated while chewing
mushy	T-mushy	none much	Puree, porridge
adherence	T-adherence	none much	Adherence, glues teeth together

Appendix II – Sensory scales for whole, raw shrimp

*Quality Index Method for whole raw shrimp/Gæðastuðulsaðferð fyrir heila rækju
Evaluation based on demerit points and their sum/Mat samkvæmt einkunnaskala*

Gæðapáttur Quality parameter		Lýsing Description	Einkunn DP																			
Heil rækja Whole shrimp	Dökk í haus Head dark- ening	Engin None	0																			
		Sumar Some (25%)	1																			
		Margar Many (50-75%)	2																			
		Allar All (75-100%)	3																			
	Litur Colour	Skær bleikur/rauður Pink/Red	0																			
		Ljósbleikur Light pink	1																			
		Gulleitur Yellowish	2																			
		Gulleitur með grárri eða grænni slikju Yellowish with gray/green overtone	3																			
	Lykt Odor	Fersk, sjávar-, þörunga Fresh, shellfish, seaweed	0																			
		Dauf lykt, minnir á tjöru, net Less odorous, tar-like, net-like	1																			
		Dauf ammoníakslykt Slight ammoniacal odor	2																			
		Greinileg ammoníakslykt, súr, ýlda Obvious ammoniacal odor, sour, putrid	3																			
Hrogn Roe	Litur hrogna Color	Kopargræn Copper green	0																			
		Upplituð Discolored	1																			
		Dökk Dark	2																			
Gæðastuðull Quality Index (0- 11) Summa stiga Total demerit points (DP):																						

Quality grading scheme - Score sheet for raw, whole shrimp

Score 5: Excellent. Color: dark red to bright pink. Roes are blue-green (copper). Strong seaweedy, marine odor. Strong sweet shrimp taste.

Score 4: Good. Color natural light pink. Roes are blue-green (copper). Weak, characteristic shrimp odor. Weak sweet shrimp taste.

Score 3: Moderate. Marine/shrimp odor is diminishing, weak "fishy odor", even slight ammonia. Color natural light pink with grey-greenish or yellowish discoloration. Roes are light green. Taste is natural not sweet to weak "fishy taste".

Score 2: Borderline. Clearly not fresh. Weak ammonia odor. Color natural light pink with grey-greenish or yellowish discoloration. Roes are discolored. Blackening on the head can be spotted. Distinct fishy taste with bitter aftertaste.

Score 1: Unfit, spoiled. Ammonia odor. Color natural light pink with grey-greenish or yellowish discoloration. Roes are dark. The blackening on the heads is extensive. Spoiled, taste with strong, bitter aftertaste.

GDA - Sensory attributes for cooked, peeled shrimp and their definitions

Sensory attribute	Short name	Scale	Definition
ODOUR			
sweet	O-sweet	none much	Sweet odour
shellfish, algae	O-shellfish	none much	Characteristic fresh odour of shrimp
vanilla	O-vanilla	none much	Vanilla, sweet heated milk
TMA	O-TMA	none much	TMA odour, reminds of dried salted fish, amine
spoilage sour	O-sour	none much	Sour odour, sour milk, spoilage sour, acetic acid
sulphur	O-sulphur	none much	Sulphur, matchstick
APPEARANCE			
red colour	A-red	light dark	Colour of red membrane
meat colour	A-colour	white yellowish	Colour of meat
FLAVOUR			
sweet	F-sweet	none much	Characteristic sweet flavour of fresh shrimp
metallic	F-metallic	none much	Characteristic metallic flavour of fresh shrimp
shellfish	F-shellfish	none much	Shellfish
pungent	F-pungent	none much	Pungent flavour, bitter
spoilage sour	F-sour	none much	Spoilage sour
TMA	F-TMA	none much	TMA flavour, reminds of dried salted fish, amine
putrid	F-putrid	none much	Putrid
off-flavour	F-off	none much	describe in comment box
TEXTURE			
soft	T-soft	firm soft	Evaluated at first bite
springy	T-springy	none much	At the beginning of chewing, rubbery, springy
juicy	T-juicy	dry juicy	Dry- draws liquid from mouth
tender	T-tender	tough tender	Evaluated while chewing
mushy	T-mushy	little much	Mushy texture, puree
crumbly	T-crumbly	none much	Easily crumbled, breaks down into small particles

Appendix III – Sensory scales for cooked cod

GDA sensory attributes for cooked cod and their description

Sensory attribute	Short name	Scale anchors	Description of attribute
<i>Odour</i>			
sweet	o-sweet	none much	Sweet odour
shellfish, algae	o-shellfish	none much	Shellfish, characteristic fresh odour
vanilla / warm milk	o-vanilla	none much	Vanilla, sweet heated milk
boiled potatoes	o-potatoes	none much	Reminds of whole warm boiled potatoes
dishcloth	o-cloth	none much	Reminds of a dishcloth (damp cloth to clean kitchen table, left for 36 h)
TMA	o-TMA	none much	TMA odour, reminds of dried salted fish, amine
spoilage sour	o-sour	none much	Sour odour, sour milk, spoilage sour, acetic acid
sulphur	o-sulphur	none much	Sulphur, matchstick
<i>Appearance</i>			
colour	a-dark	light dark	Sample surface. Light; white colour, Dark; yellowish, brownish, grey
heterogenous	a-hetero	homogenous heterogenous	Sample surface. Heterogenous, discoloured, stains
white precipitation	a-prec	none much	White precipitation on the sample surface
flakiness	a-flakes	none much	The fish portion slides into flakes when pressed with the fork
<i>Flavour</i>			
salt	f-salt	none much	Salty taste
metallic	f-metallic	none much	Characteristic metallic flavour of fresh cod
sweet	f-sweet	none much	Characteristic sweet flavour of very fresh (boiled cod)
pungent	f-pungent	none much	Pungent flavour, bitter
acidic	f-acidic	none much	Acidic flavour, not spoilage sour
spoilage sour	f-sour	none much	Sour taste, spoilage sour
TMA	f-TMA	none much	TMA flavour, reminds of dried salted fish, amine
putrid	f-putrid	none much	Strength of putrid flavour
<i>Texture</i>			
soft	t-soft	firm soft	Evaluate how firm or soft the fish is during the first bite
juicy	t-juicy	dry juicy	Dry; draws juice from the mouth
tender	t-tender	tough tender	Evaluated after chewing several times
mushy	t-mushy	none much	Mushy texture
astringent	t-astringent	none much	Astringent texture, tannin (dry red wine)
rubbery	t-rubbery	none much	Rubbery texture, springy

Scoring scale for freshness evaluation of cooked fillets (modified Torry scale)

Odour	Flavour	score
Initially weak odour of sweet, boiled milk, starchy followed by strengthening of these odours	Watery, metallic, starchy. Initially no sweetness but meaty flavours with slight sweetness may develop	10
Shellfish, seaweed, boiled meat	Sweet, meaty, characteristic	9
Loss of odour, neutral odour	Sweet and characteristic flavours but reduced in intensity	8
Woodshavings, woodsap, vanillin	Neutral	7
Condensed milk, boiled potato	Insidid	6
Milk jug odours, boiled clothes- like	Slight sourness, trace of off-flavours	5
Lactic acid, sour milk, TMA	Slight bitterness, sour, off-flavours, TMA	4
Lower fatty acids (eg acetic or butyric acids) composed grass, soapy, turnipy, tallowy	Strong bitter, rubber, slight sulphide	3

Appendix IV – Results for whole, gutted salmon
GDA results for odor (O) and appearance (A) attributes

Group	O-sweet	O-metallic	O-oil	O-acid	O-earthy	O-sour	O-rancid	O-queasy	O-putrid	A-precipit.	A-heterog.	A-colour	A-yellow l.	A-droplets.
Day 3														
B	33	22	18	15	17 b	3 a	10 b	4	2	23	35	36	35	51
C	35	24	18	11	23 a	4 a	15 a	4	2	26	38	37	35	47
D	36	25	23	12	16 b	1 b	8 b	3	0	23	38	40	37	48
K	38	26	21	14	17 b	1 b	5 b	3	0	23	38	39	38	40
<i>p-value</i>	0,347	0,496	0,218	0,383	0,023 *	0,000 ***	0,004 **	0,120	0,029 *	0,822	0,654	0,620	0,675	0,115
Day 6														
B	32	24	17	11	18	1	13	2	1	34 b	39	39 a	29	46
C	34	25	17	9	17	1	12	2	1	43 a	37	34	26	48
D	34	31	19	13	15	2	11	4	1	40	38	30 b	26	41
K	36	26	18	11	16	1	9	3	1	39	34	29 b	26	43
<i>p-value</i>	0,404	0,097 <i>ms</i>	0,762	0,307	0,791	0,667	0,647	0,420	0,573	0,027 *	0,420	0,002 **	0,758	0,156
Day 10														
B	35	23	23	12	16	1	12	5	1	35	39	40	28	45
C	35	24	22	11	14	1	6	3	1	33	42	38	27	39 b
D	35	25	21	13	14	1	8	4	1	37	34	38	30	47
K	36	22	22	13	14	1	8	5	0	39	37	44	37	50 a
<i>p-value</i>	0,953	0,671	0,728	0,688	0,834	0,139	0,150	0,447	0,480	0,365	0,096 <i>ms</i>	0,304	0,172	0,056 <i>ms</i>
Day 14														
B	20	11	10	11	17	3	10	3	1	36	34	42	29	43
C	21	11	11	15	12	3	9	4	1	38	34	39	31	47
D	17	10	12	16	11	2	7	3	1	40	29	37	31	37 b
K	21	11	10	13	14	2	8	4	1	40	34	43	37	50 a
<i>p-value</i>	0,323	0,878	0,775	0,391	0,187	0,816	0,801	0,831	0,325	0,576	0,252	0,355	0,202	0,027 *
Day 17														
B	16	13	6	13	14	14	8	10 b	14 b	40	36	40	29	38
C	15	13	7	11	16	9 b	11	10 b	9 bc	45	40	38	30	34
D	20 a	15 a	8	12	16	12	9	9 b	4 c	40	36	40	26	34
K	10 b	9 b	5	6	14	21 a	9	17 a	21 a	43	37	43	33	40
<i>p-value</i>	0,005 **	0,041 *	0,126	0,129	0,829	0,023 *	0,497	0,019 *	0,000 ***	0,187	0,777	0,325	0,160	0,481

Whole, gutted salmon - GDA results for flavor (F) and texture (T) attributes

Group	F-sweet	F-metallic	F-oil	F-acid	F-earthy	F-sour	F-rancid	F-queasy	T-soft	T-juicy	T-tender	T-mushy	T-adherence
Day 3													
B	41	29	24	12	17	2 ab	5	4	53	44	58	26	47
C	38	30	23	13	16	2 a	7 a	3	51	40	56	31	50
D	39	32	27	13	16	1 bc	2	3	53	40	56	28	49
K	40	30	27	13	17	1 c	3 b	3	53	40	56	25	51
<i>p-value</i>	0,865	0,855	0,493	0,933	0,785	0,008 **	0,039 *	0,780	0,916	0,281	0,806	0,377	0,430
Day 6													
B	37	32	20	16	17	2	7	3	64	53	66	32	36
C	36	32	20	12	15	1	7	2	59	50	62	31	38
D	36	32	21	14	18	1	6	3	62	48	61	35	37
K	35	29	19	16	17	1	7	3	62	49	59	32	36
<i>p-value</i>	0,862	0,512	0,686	0,509	0,839	0,731	0,854	0,958	0,184	0,480	0,085 ms	0,669	0,670
Day 10													
B	38	28	24	17	16	1	6	5	59	53	62	36	37
C	40	30	25	18	15	2	4	4	62	55	62	37	42
D	40	29	27	18	16	1	5	3	63	58	63	35	40
K	38	30	25	17	17	1	6	4	61	56	63	31	38
<i>p-value</i>	0,866	0,742	0,665	0,998	0,896	0,829	0,447	0,557	0,569	0,669	0,913	0,469	0,291
Day 14													
B	20	19	11	17	15	2	4	3	57	43	58	22	38
C	20	20	13	18	14	4	2	5	58	39	60	24	42
D	20	20	10	21	14	2	3	4	54	40	58	23	38
K	20	18	11	18	17	2	8	4	54	38	57	25	38
<i>p-value</i>	0,999	0,872	0,577	0,597	0,767	0,690	0,089 ms	0,814	0,504	0,606	0,854	0,812	0,388
Day 17													
B	20	14	10	18	14	14	10	15	60	43	62	44	34
C	24	16	10	20	14	12	12	11	69	54	71	48	39
D	25	15	13	19	13	7	7	13	66	49	65	43	37
K	11	13	7	16	13	19	12	21	54	42	56	44	37
<i>p-value</i>	0,055 ms	0,928	0,063 ms	0,815	0,961	0,091 ms	0,258	0,223	0,213	0,230	0,247	0,598	0,437

Appendix V - Whole, gutted salmon

Appendix VI - Chilled shrimp 5 days post-catch

Control 1

A 1

B 1

Control 2

A 2

B 2

Appendix VII – Results for whole, gutted cod

Table A - Mean values for GDA sensory attributes of cooked samples

Day of storage: days post-catch.

Different letters within a column per storage day represent a significant difference between the two groups.

The results are based on data from 12 panelists on day 3 and 9 panelists on day 6.

Group	o-sweet	o-shellfish	o-vanilla	o-potatoes	o-cloth	o-TMA	o-sour	o-sulphur	a-dark	a-hetero.	a-prec.	a-flakes		
Day 3														
K	43	28	21	10	2	0	0	0	16	20	12	69		
C	46	31	16	11	2	0	0	0	20	24	15	59		
D	43	28	16	10	3	0	1	0	17	22	11	62		
p-value	0,696	0,295	0,368	0,748	0,284	0,240	0,578	0,734	0,090 ms	0,442	0,145	0,076 ms		
Day 6														
K	35	24	14	15 a	4	3	1	0	23	23	11	64		
C	32	27	11	13	5	2	1	0	25 a	32 a	14	64		
D	39	30	12	9 b	2	0	0	0	16 b	17 b	16	61		
p-value	0,192	0,219	0,172	0,033 *	0,345	0,120	0,133	0,499	0,043 *	0,013 *	0,142	0,866		
Group	f-salt	f-metallic	f-sweet	f-pungent	f-acidic	f-sour	f-TMA	f-putrid	t-soft	t-juicy	t-tender	t-mushy	t-astringent	t-rubbery
Day 3														
K	7	45 a	45	2	1	0	0	0	61 a	64	66	20	10 b	8
C	5	38 b	42	3	3	0	0	0	54 b	58	63	24	13	13
D	7	34 b	43	3	0	1	0	0	60 a	61	64	25	15 a	10
p-value	0,539	0,007 **	0,505	0,707	0,190	0,514	0,877	0,845	0,014 *	0,277	0,674	0,389	0,042 *	0,286
Day 6														
K	10	27	28 b	6	3	1	2	0	72 a	63	73	47	12	6
C	7	29	32 b	5	4	2	1	0	71 a	64	75	46 a	12	7
D	9	34	40 a	2	2	0	0	0	62 b	64	69	33 b	12	7
p-value	0,517	0,181	0,008 **	0,111	0,248	0,531	0,100	0,576	0,005 **	0,964	0,086 ms	0,053 *	0,899	0,122

ms (marginal significance, $p = 0,05-0,10$); * ($p < 0,05$); ** ($p < 0,01$).

Table B - Mean values for GDA sensory attributes for lot 1 - cooked samples

Day: days from filleting (3 days post-catch).

Different letters within a column per storage day represent a significant difference between the two groups. The results are based on data from 9 panellists on day 3 and 7 panellists on day 7. Results for odor (o-) and appearance (a-) attributes on day 10 are based on data from 6 panellists but only three panellists evaluated flavor (f-) and texture (t-) of all samples on day 10. Therefore these results are not included.

Group	o-sweet	o-shellfish	o-vanilla	o-potatoes	o-cloth	o-TMA	o-sour	o-sulphur	a-dark	a-hetero.	a-prec.	a-flakes		
Day 3														
K1	36	29	14	11	2	1	1	0	16	18	20	63		
C1	32	29	14	10	2	0	1	0	14	15	24	60		
D1	32	27	11	12	3	1	1	0	14	13	20	57		
p-value	0,272	0,721	0,377	0,690	0,889	0,649	0,826	0,390	0,606	0,272	0,257	0,586		
Day 7														
K1	27	13	13	16	11 b	3	3	1	21	23 b	35	46		
C1	20	7	12	19	18 a	8	2	1	27	35 a	34	50		
D1	23	8	11	18	19 a	6	2	1	26	28	31	52		
p-value	0,162	0,052 ms	0,679	0,673	0,010 *	0,201	0,459	0,531	0,117	0,019 *	0,268	0,397		
Day 10														
K1	14	10	11	23	20	25	11	3	37 a	42	34	42		
C1	12	10	12	27 a	23	18	5	2	29 b	37	40	44		
D1	14	10	11	19 b	18	23	9	3	32	40	33	42		
p-value	0,335	0,913	0,332	0,016 *	0,078 ms	0,458	0,159	0,584	0,053 ms	0,323	0,211	0,960		
Group	f-salt	f-metallic	f-sweet	f-pungent	f-acidic	f-sour	f-TMA	f-putrid	t-soft	t-juicy	t-tender	t-mushy	t-astringent	t-rubbery
Day 3														
K1	10	34	36	7	2	1	1	0	65	68	73	33	12	6 b
C1	10	33	37	3	2	1	0	0	61 b	63	63	34	20	10 a
D1	9	34	43	3	2	1	0	0	69 a	68	72	34	13	6 b
p-value	0,758	0,944	0,098 ms	0,226	0,807	0,783	0,365	0,259	0,040 *	0,227	0,179	0,943	0,114	0,006 **
Day 7														
K1	4	25	24 a	16	4	0	1	1 b	58	55	64	39	13	4
C1	4	18	18 b	16	4	2	4	1 a	64	58	64	39	9	4
D1	3	21	18	18	3	3	4	1	59	55	61	39	15	5
p-value	0,722	0,182	0,059 ms	0,908	0,904	0,200	0,131	0,074 ms	0,553	0,686	0,669	0,994	0,238	0,432

ms (marginal significance, $p = 0,05-0,10$); * ($p < 0,05$); ** ($p < 0,01$); *** ($p < 0,001$).

Table C – Mean values for GDA sensory attributes for lot 2 - cooked samples

Day: days from filleting (6 days post-catch).

Different letters within a column per storage day represent a significant difference between the two groups. The results are based on data from 8 panellists on day 3. Results for odor (o-) and appearance (a-) attributes on day 6 are based on data from 7 panelists but results for flavour (f-) and texture (t-) are based on data from 5 panelists.

Group	o-sweet	o-shellfish	o-vanilla	o-potatoes	o-cloth	o-TMA	o-sour	o-sulphur	a-dark	a-hetero.	a-prec.	a-flakes
Day 3												
K2	31	14	13	17	9	4	1	1	24	26	27	54
C2	32	18	14	18	11	4	1	0	18	21	24	58
D2	26	15	15	22	9	3	2	0	20	24	25	57
p-value	0,308	0,140	0,732	0,420	0,720	0,817	0,701	0,423	0,591	0,634	0,755	0,608
Day 6												
K2	19	13	17	27	23	14	9	1	35	33	38	42
C2	21	13	15	19	23	13	6	1	29	34	31	35
D2	22	12	17	22	22	7	4	1	28	30	36	46
p-value	0,775	0,953	0,653	0,143	0,954	0,269	0,176	0,324	0,145	0,677	0,097 ms	0,116

Group	f-salt	f-metallic	f-sweet	f-pungent	f-acidic	f-sour	f-TMA	f-putrid	t-soft	t-juicy	t-tender	t-mushy	t-astringent	t-rubbery
Day 3														
K2	4	27	26 b	15	2	1	3	1	64	56	65	44	16	5
C2	5	32	32 a	14	2	1	2	2	64	61	64	45	15	5
D2	4	21	25 b	15	3	2	2	2	64	59	69	42	15	7
p-value	0,382	0,061 ms	0,037 *	0,904	0,634	0,101	0,466	0,464	0,998	0,394	0,474	0,919	0,922	0,573
Day 6														
K2	10	25	26	12	0	6	10	0	62	59	62	41	16	5
C2	9	31	27	15	0	2	4	0	62	57	60	35	13	8
D2	9	23	28	11	1	4	4	0	61	57	63	29	15	6
p-value	0,715	0,254	0,881	0,757	0,564	0,126	0,120	0,656	0,973	0,811	0,594	0,066 ms	0,418	0,211

ms (marginal significance, p = 0,05-0,10); * (p < 0,05); ** (p < 0,01).

Appendix VIII - Whole, gutted cod

